

Naturalista sicil., S. IV, XLVII (1), 2023, pp. 99-104

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8155676>

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EUROPEAN RED LISTS STATE OF PLAY. BEES AND OTHER POLLINATORS

Il punto sulle Liste Rosse Europee. Api ed altri impollinatori

Pollinators are threatened and are undergoing a dangerous decline in terms of populations and species, exposing some to a real risk of extinction.

IMPORTANCE OF THE RED LISTS

Established in 1964, the International Union for Conservation of Nature's Red List of Threatened Species has evolved to become the world's most comprehensive information source on the global extinction risk status of animal and plant species.

When starting the drafting of a new red list, an entire taxonomic group is taken into consideration. Generally, all world major experts who engage with this group are consulted. Of course, the greater the size of the group and the number of species involved, the greater the difficulties to be overcome to evaluate the entire group. Some taxonomic groups enjoy greater popularity among scholars for several reasons, sometimes they are simply more pleasing to the human eye. Let us think, for example, of groups such as birds and mammals. In this case, the number of enthusiasts who collect data in nature is also greater and as is evident, a greater number of scholars available results in greater detail and quantity of information for the assessment of the extinction risk. However, when we consider invertebrates, only a few groups of organisms are pleasing, such as butterflies and some iridescent metallic-colored beetles.

If, on the other hand, we consider very numerous and unattractive

groups such as wild bees and hoverflies, the evaluation starts at a disadvantage. To have an adequate taxonomic knowledge of these so numerous and difficult groups today, it would have been necessary in the past decades to train an important number of taxonomists, but this has not happened. The lack of experts has as a further consequence the absence of appropriate iconographic and diagnostic literature on the species, especially in areas with a higher degree of biodiversity such as the Mediterranean. This also discouraged the young non-specialist enthusiasts, who could not have the material to identify the species. Despite this, it has been possible to assess the risk of extinction for wild bees and, currently, the red list of hoverflies is being published, which therefore completes the three main groups of wild pollinators. The European red lists on the three most important pollinator groups include 1965 species of wild bees, 890 species of helicopter flies and 482 species of butterflies.

The publication of European red lists also favors the drafting of national red lists. For Italy, for example, a national red list of butterfly and bees has been published (BALLETO *et al.*, 2015; QUARANTA *et al.*, 2018). For bees, an updated national checklist is in preparation, and it has so far been possible to draw up an extinction risk assessment for only a small part of the entire national fauna, but it is still a start.

The honeybee is by far the most important pollinator, since it is raised by man, however the turnover of the main product of beekeeping, honey, is far less important than the monetary value attributable to the pollinating action of the honeybee for agricultural crops, which is 20 times as much (GALLAI *et al.*, 2009). Furthermore, the value of pollination of natural flora should not be overlooked, which in turn supports the general biodiversity of small vertebrates and invertebrates.

The extinction risk assessment procedure follows strict rules, based not so much on the rarity and specialization of a species, but on the population trend. For a taxon to be assigned a higher risk category, it must decline by 30% over 10 years, which is a highly risky value for the existence of a species. Furthermore, to monitor the changing status of biodiversity, it is essential to reassess species periodically. This reassessment may result in species moving into a different Red List Category for non-genuine or genuine reasons.

The categories of extinction risk are three, Vulnerable, Endangered and Critically Endangered.

When the set of available information is not sufficient to issue a solid assessment, a species is designated as a data deficient, in a suspended judgment until it acquires added information through scientific research. From the processing of data collected to prepare the European red lists of bees, it emerges that the pattern of distribution of Data Deficient species is primarily concentrated in the Mediterranean region. This deficiency may be due to

insufficient, or even complete lack of, taxonomic expertise for large parts of the European bee fauna in the Iberian, Italian and Balkan peninsulas.

EUROPEAN MONITORING SCHEME AND TREND INDICATORS

Monitoring is therefore the essential tool to assess over time if a species is declining. In the United Kingdom, monitoring of many species has been underway for some years, which are observed annually with methods appropriate for each type of organism, making extensive use of teams of volunteers, from whom data are obtained and uploaded to a computer platform. These data, together with others of various origins, are processed with statistical tools by teams of ecological experts and taxonomists and converge into general population trend indicators. Pollinator groups such as wild bees, hoverflies and butterflies are also evaluated among these organisms. Butterflies are also the subject of a European monitoring scheme, the European Butterfly Monitoring Scheme, which takes place in various European countries, and they too are monitored by volunteer citizen scientists, and the data come together to form some indicators.

Indicators should also be able to perceive the effect of conservation measures put in place to halt the decline. Many of these measures have been adopted through the agricultural policies of the European Union and yet, despite a lot of money spent over a few decades, there does not seem to be an appreciable halt in the decline of biodiversity. One of the possible explanations put forward for this failure is that organisms widely used as indicators of biodiversity, birds, which with their flight mostly intersect areas of hundreds or thousands of square kilometers, are not the most suitable for measuring interventions at the agricultural district level, which by their nature, on the other hand, involve areas of a few hectares. From this consideration a new strategy emerged, that of using invertebrate organisms, which are sensitive to changes affecting small areas such as those of a farm.

The IUCN European Red Lists (VAN SWAY *et al.*, 2010; NIETO *et al.*, 2014) indicate that 37% of bee species and 31% of butterfly species have declining populations and 9% of all bees, 26% of bumble bees, and 19% of butterflies are classified as threatened, while 57% of bees were data deficient and so could not be assessed. The species richness of bees increases from north to south in Europe, with the highest species richness being found in the Mediterranean climate zone. In particular, the Iberian, Italian and Balkan peninsulas are important areas of species richness.

The highest concentration of threatened pollinators, both bees and butterflies, are in central, eastern, and south-eastern Europe, especially in fragile habi-

tats like mountains. In these same areas we find the highest concentration of endemism. About 20% (~ 400 species) of bee fauna, and about 16% (164 of 983 species) of hoverfly fauna is endemic to Europe (SPEIGHT, 2020). There are 482 butterfly species documented in Europe with almost a third of these endemic to Europe; Southern Europe has a high number of endemic species, for which the European Union has a high responsibility, but about which little is known despite their important contribution to biodiversity and ecosystem health in Europe.

NATIONAL RED LISTS OF THREATENED SPECIES

The European red lists, once produced, provide the starting point for creating national red lists in the various member states of the European Union. In each national red list, the extinction risk category assigned to each species is not infrequently different from that assigned to it in the European list. This is not surprising. Each species, in fact, is characterized by its own range of distribution and different nations are inevitably found either in the center or on the periphery of this area where the vulnerability of the species can vary; above all, the intensity of the threats to which each species is subjected may vary in different countries, and the response of each local population of the species to the variations in the ecological niches created in different localities as well. For this last aspect let us think, for example, of bumblebee populations that in Northern Europe we find in the plains but on the other hand in Southern Europe, to meet their winter cold needs, must necessarily be located on Apennine reliefs above a certain altitude.

THREATS

Across Europe, the relative importance of different threats varies widely across its biogeographic regions and countries. Each species assessment lists the major threats affecting the specific pollinator. Among the many threats, the major are linked to modern agriculture, as are the widespread use of agri-chemicals, agricultural expansion, and intensification with, in particular, shifting agricultural practice and increasing intensification of farming.

ACTION PLANS

The monitoring of the population trend of wild bee species has the final aim of identifying, together with the red lists, the species most in

need of protection measures. These are articulated in Action Plans. These are products for conservation of threatened pollinator species in the European Union, developed in the framework of a collaboration with experts from the IUCN Species Survival Commission. The group's mission is to save threatened species by increasing the effectiveness of conservation efforts worldwide. Five first steps of the methodology to produce the final Conservation Action Plans for the European pollinators, are: 1) Preparation, 2) Status Review, 3) Building a Vision and Goals, 4) Analyzing Threats, setting objectives and performance indicators, and 5) Planning the actions.

After taking into consideration some groups of pollinators linked to different fragile and threatened habitats, it was chosen to carry out the conservation of Teasel Bees as a first Action Plan. Many wild bee species are highly specialized in pollen plants. This multi-species plan will focus on bee species which are specialized in teasel plants (Dipsacaceae), such as *Scabiosa*, *Knautia* etc. In addition to habitat conservation and restoration, this project may include reintroduction efforts in some EU Member States. Moreover, these species could be good for citizen science and public engagement as they are easy to identify and rely on teasel species which are recognizable plants across Europe.

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